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Something is rotten in the state...

History and the Political Ethos Represented on Pushkin's Stage: The Dramatic Poet and the Historian

At first sight it may seem at least strange to ascribe the occupation *h i s t o r i a n* to a person whom we generally bear in mind as a *p o e t*. Surely, historical scholarship and poetry (or art) are rather different areas of the human intellect. It was probably ARISTOTLE who first made clear the distinction between history and poetry, saying:

ὁ γὰρ ἱστορικὸς καὶ ὁ ποιητὴς [...] τούτῳ διαφέρει, τῷ τὸν μὲν τὰ γενόμενα λέγειν, τὸν δὲ οἷα ἂν γένοιτο. διὸ καὶ φιλοσοφώτερον καὶ σπουδαιότερον ποίησις ἐστίν, ἢ μὲν γὰρ ποιήσις μᾶλλον τὰ καθόλου, ἢ δ' ἱστορία τὰ καθ' ἕκαστον λέγει. ἔστι δὲ καθόλου μὲν, τῷ ποίῳ τὰ ποί' ἅττα συμβαίνει λέγειν ἢ πράττειν κατὰ τὸ εἶκός ἢ τὸ ἀναγκαῖον οὐ στοχάζεται ἢ ποιήσις ὀνόματα ἐπιτιθεμένη. τὰ δὲ καθ' ἕκαστων, τί Ἀλκιβιάδης ἔπραξεν ἢ τί ἔπαθεν. [...] ἐπὶ δὲ τῆς τραγωδίας τῶν γενομένων ὀνομάτων ἀντέχονται. αἴτιον δέ, ὅτι πιθανόν ἐστὶ τὸ δυνατόν· τὰ μὲν οὖν μὴ γενόμενα οὕτω πιστεύομεν εἶναι δυνατά, τὰ δὲ γενόμενα φανερόν ὅτι δυνατά, οὐ γὰρ ἐγένετο, εἰ ἦν ἀδύνατα.¹

The historian and the poet differ [...] in that the former tells what had happened, while the latter what may happen. Poetry is therefore more philosophical and weightier than history because poetry, on the one hand, would rather tell about the universal, while history, on the other, would tell about the particular. Universal is how one speaks or acts in a certain way, according to probability or necessity; this is what poetry aims at, though applying individual names. Particular is, for example, what Alcibiades did or what happened to him. [...] In tragedies they [sc. the tragic poets] cleave to historical names. The reason for this is that the possible is credible; what did not actually happen we would not believe to be possible, but it is clear that what had happened is possible because it would certainly not have happened if it had been impossible.²

ARISTOTLE then goes on:

κἂν ἄρα συμβῆ γεινόμενα ποιεῖν, οὐδὲν ἥττον ποιητῆς ἐστὶ, τῶν γὰρ γενομένων ἔνια οὐδὲν κωλύει τοιαῦτα εἶναι, οἷα ἂν εἰκὸς γενέσθαι καὶ δυνατὰ γενέσθαι· καθ' ὃ ἐκεῖνος αὐτῶν ποιητῆς ἐστὶ.³

And if he writes about events that had actually happened, he is no less a poet because with some of the events that had actually taken place there is no reason why they should not be of such sort as they would be upon probability and possibility. In this way he is the poet of those events.

(spacings mine - M.M.)

Although Aristotle did not know Pushkin's *Boris Godunov*, he seems to have clearly grasped what lies at the bottom of the modern phrase *historical drama*.⁴ Both that Pushkin very heavily relies on a historian's account and that he assigns in his play a very significant role to a chronicler show that history (the historical events he chose to dramatize) for him meant not only a story or a series of stories he could use in his play. *Boris Godunov* is historical not in a superficial sense as so-called historical dramas, novels or even operas usually are. For Pushkin history is the *subject* of his tragedy. To put it in another way, he has managed to grasp the spirit of history in his chronicle-drama. It is not at all by chance that Pushkin has chosen Shakespeare's chronicle-plays as artistic samples for his historical drama. Just as he has used Karamzin and, perhaps to a lesser extent, Tacitus as his guides in the realm of history, he has followed Shakespeare in making poetry of history. *Boris Godunov* is a historical tragedy in the *modern sense*, i.e. without the pathos so characteristic of romantic historical dramas. This means that the characters entirely lack idealization which is typical of romantic heroes. I will point out that the peculiar way Pushkin handles the question of *pathos* in the individual characters as well as in the whole of the drama provides an essential clue for the interpretation.

I will try to reveal how the machinery of politics works in *Boris Godunov*, i.e. show the way Pushkin grasped how *politicians* think and act in a particular situation when things are drawing to a crisis and for some of the participants it is, in the strict sense of the word, a matter of life and death. What is perhaps most important and most interesting in this respect is how all this can be depicted in a work of art in an authentic way. To illustrate how the theme of politics appears, how it is elaborated and how it becomes a substantial element of the drama, I found it most expedient first to dwell on Shuisky, who is one of the key figures in the play, as well as on some of the minor characters such as Basmanov and the boyar Pushkin. Of course, mention will be made of the Pretender who proves to be very resolute and determined in pursuing his political aims. The poet has so built these characters that through their thoughts and actions the disposition of the *Homo politicus* as such can most appropriately be shown. I will not dwell long on the protagonist, Boris Godunov: he is not the sort of *homo politicus* who is suitable for the discussion here because he is not an *active* participant in

the political game represented in this play. This is the source of his tragedy: his inability to accept the challenge. Thus he is rather a v i c t i m of the game than a player in it.

Boris Godunov is a tragic character since the tragic action -- everything in the play that has a tragic bearing -- is focussed in him; yet the way the drama is composed throws a peculiar light upon his figure. Therefore it is worth while to examine Pushkin's composition from this point of view. It is noteworthy how the individual scenes in the play follow one another. I will point out that in the interpretation of the drama this has a decisive bearing.

Although the drama is about Boris Godunov, it is only in Scene 4 that he first appears. Why has the poet so composed his play that his protagonist comes on the stage relatively so late? He must have had some reason for this delay. It therefore deserves attention to examine the first three scenes.

By placing the dialogue between the princes Vorotinsky and Shuisky right at the beginning of the play Pushkin introduces the theme of political manipulation into the drama. They are speculating upon the chances of Godunov's accepting the throne. However, it is not quite precise to say that b o t h of these men are trying to guess the fate of the Russian crown: it is only the naïve Vorotinsky who is guessing while Shuisky, the artful dodger, appears to k n o w e x a c t l y what will happen. This is clear from his very first utterance: what he replies to his counterpart who asks him "how will this turbulence end?" shows a man of experience, one who is well versed in political matters. He is the one of the two who sees behind the scenes. He is entirely familiar with the situation: why Godunov hesitates, what and why had happened in Uglich to the young Tsarevich, etc. With this knowledge he can easily calculate the future. At the same time, however, he betrays to us that he lacks one trait that is indispensable for acquiring the supreme power: a u d a c i t y. This is the reason why he will not be Tsar instead of Godunov: at this moment he does not w i s h to compete with Godunov. This is how he gives to Vorotinsky the reasons for their being pushed into the background:

?> F<;, &@H &F, - " <Z...

He [sc. Boris] has dared, that is all -- but we...

Shuisky makes Vorotinsky believe that it is the lack of boldness which prevented him from competing with Godunov for the throne. It is, in fact, not synchrony what is in question here (sc. that Godunov dared to do what Shuisky did not) but that Shuisky covertly suggests his partner to follow suit. However, the attentive recipient of the play will not make Vorotinsky's mistake, i.e. will not believe Shuisky. Pushkin gives in the form of a masterly concealed hint a key for the right interpretation of Shuisky's behaviour as well as of the line cited above. This is Boris Godunov's characterization of Shuisky in the scene *The Palace of the Tsar* just prior to Shuisky's entering:

! S J 6 F 8 @ < J > , * @ : 0 > @ * @ & , D b H \:

I8:@>R4&Z6, >@ F <, : Z 6 4 :J8"&Z6...

*But you should not believe Shuisky:
He is pliable but bold and cunning...
(spacings mine: M.M.)*

You should not believe the bold Shuisky, Godunov says. Retrospectively, in the light of the tsar's characterization of Shuisky it is not true what Shuisky says to Vorotinsky about the lack of his boldness. It has become clear that Shuisky only wanted to see through his partner and get to know his innermost thoughts.

It was his boldness that enabled Godunov to step on the road that has led him to the immediate vicinity of the throne, and it is the same boldness that will, as Shuisky rightly sees, make him overstep his moral scruples to seize power. Yet this will also ruin him because his choice will prove to be a miscalculation on the long run. (Daring, as we will see later, will also make the young monk, Grigory able to contend with Godunov; in fact, this is one of the secrets of his success.) As for Shuisky, his lack of audacity in a crucial moment has prevented him from upsetting Godunov's plans. When Vorotinsky asks him why he did not expose the child-murderer upon returning from Uglich where he had been sent (by Godunov) to investigate the circumstances of the Tsarevich's mysterious death, his answer is that if he had then revealed the truth, he would have been "sent to gaol, / and at the right hour, ... / in the deaf dungeon silently strangled." At this point it seems worth while to observe a perhaps not so conspicuous yet a rather deep compositional analogy between the passage just cited and referred to and another one, in which the Pretender, after he had revealed himself to Marina, the Polish nobleman's daughter, "explains" to his counterpart why it is not advisable for her to lay bare the truth about him. For the sake of perspicuity I now cite both passages in full:

SJ6F846

*! RH@ <>, \$Z:@ *,"H\?
%F, @\$Xb&4H\ K,@*@DJ? =@ P"D\
=" &F, (:b*, : @R"<4 '@*J>@&"
%F,<J &>4<": JT"<4 '@*J>@&"
AJF8"6, (@ \$ J&,D4: b &@ &F,<
#@D4F H@HR"F, (@ \$Z D"2J&,D4;
! H"< <,>b 0 F@F:" :4 \$ & 2"H@R,>|,
)" & *@\$DZ6 R"F, 8"8 *b*` <@,(@,
% (:JN@6 H`D\<, H4N@>|8@ \$ 2"*"&4:4.*

Shuisky

*What could I do?
Should I have revealed it to Feodor? The Tsar
Looked at everything through Godunov's eyes,*

*Heard everything through Godunov's ears:
But should I have persuaded him about everything,
Boris would have promptly dissuaded him.
As for me, I would have been sent to gaol,
And at the right hour, just as my uncle,
In the deaf dungeon silently strangled.*

and

[;"D4>" !,F:4 b H&@6 *,D2@FH>Z6 @\$<">
1"D">., BD,* &F,<4 @\$>"DJ0J?]

E"<@2&">,P

=, <>4T\ :4 HZ RH@ b H,\$b \$@`F\?
QH@ \$@:., B@&,DbH B@:\F8@6 *,&.,
Q,< DJFF8@<J P"D,&4RJ? - =@ 2>"6,
QH@ >4 8@D@:\, >4 B"B", >4 &.:<@04
=, *J<"H @ BD"&*, F:@& <@4N.
)4<4HD46 b 4:\>,H - RH@ 4< 2" *::@?
=@ b BD,*:@(D"2*@D@& 4 &@6>Z.
3< ^H@ :4T\ 4 >J0>@, 4 H,\$b,
;bH,0>4P"! B@&,D\, <@:R"H\ 2"FH"&bH.

[*Marina* What if your reckless fraud
I sooner reveal before everybody?]

Pretender Surely you do not think that I fear you?
That they will believe a Polish maiden more
Than the Russian Tsarevich? -- Be aware of
That neither the king, nor the pope, nor the nobles
Seek the truth in my words.
Dimitry or not: what do they care about that?
I am a pretext for discord and war.
This is the only thing they need; and you,
Trouble-maker! believe me, you will be silenced.

Both Shuisky and the Pretender have a good grip of their situation -- necessarily because they have no other choice. It is their very existence what is at stake. Shuisky, on the one hand, finds himself in such a situation in which he has very restrained opportunities. The Pretender,

on the other hand, moves in a track where there only remains for him a substantially limited scope in which to act. In other words, they have to play the role of the *p o l i t i c i a n*: they are active participants in the political game.

On the level of the composition there is a striking parallel in the text of the two citations. The point in both passages is concealed in the last line where the speaker expounds the reason (the justification) why it was not, or would not, be expedient to reveal the truth. In Shuisky's speech the main character of this line is *s i l e n c e*: out of the five words in the Russian text two explicitly express silence (*:.JN@6: deaf* and *H4N@>|8@: silently*) and two others refer implicitly to it (*H'D\<,: dungeon* and *\$ 2"*"&4:4: strangled*). The words are arranged in a finely balanced symmetry, so that each explicit "silence-word" is supported by an allusion to silence: *H'D\<*, is placed beside *:.JN@6* as *\$ 2"*"&4:4* beside *H4N@>|8@*. The supplementation in both pairs of words serves the same purpose, viz. to give a sinister meaning to the originally neutral sense. The adjective *:.JN@6* gets a noun and with this particular noun the attributive locution gains the signification of a dark, damp and cold place where one may expect the worst. The construction in the second half of the line is very similar: the adverb *H4N@>|8@* gets a verb and thus the expectation anticipated by *:.JN@6 H'D\<*, is justified. The verb adds to the effect of the phrase because it carries a much stronger impact than its pair in the structure (the noun *H'D\<*,). Thus the force of the structure is significantly enhanced. The verb is placed in an emphasized position: at the end of the line and the sentence. Of course, this process takes only a flash as we read, or listen to, the sentence, yet this is what presumably proceeds in our mind in that moment. (It is remarkable that the *s e m a n t i c a l l y* main words, upon which the whole sentence rests, are not those that *g r a m m a t i c a l l y* govern the clause: *deaf* is an epithet of a noun, *silently* an adverb that depends on a verb).⁵

The Pretender in his speech "predicts" to Marina that she will not unmask him because if she tried, she "will be silenced". It is the motif of silence (silencing) again that ends the speech. The verb *<@:R"H\ 2"FH"&bH (silence)* is set at the end of the line and the sentence (remember the position of *\$ 2"*"&4:4 (strangled)* in Shuisky's speech). The use of the word *<@:R"H\ 2"FH"&bH* by the Pretender here is of course euphemism: it is clear that he actually means *m u r d e r e d* which is a word equal in rank with *s t r a n g l e d* used in the previous passage cited. This part of the dialogue between Marina and the Pretender therefore recalls Shuisky and Vorotinsky's scene, as the end of the drama, the *s t r a n g l i n g* of Godunov's family will pick up the Shuisky-Vorotinsky scene. I will show that this compositional contrivance of the poet has a special bearing upon the final interpretation of the drama.

To return to the scene of Shuisky and Vorotinsky, it deserves a remark to answer the question that may arise here: why does Pushkin so construct that scene, viz. why does he put Shuisky's otherwise insignificant partner on the stage (who does not appear later any more in the play) instead of using for this purpose some other figure? The answer is, I think, that Vorotinsky's figure serves as a foil to Shuisky's: through his naïveté as a contrast, he em-

phasizes Shuisky's shrewdness. Similarly, Marina in confrontation with her courtier proves naïve in that she thinks she will be able to ruin him by unmasking him.

Each of the two passages cited above deals with the truth about the fate of the small Tsarevich who had died a mysterious death in Uglich. Since the fate of the Tsarevich serves as the basis of both the plot and the poetic composition of the play, it will be very useful to examine what these figures have to say about it. Each of the characters who speak in these excerpts (including Vorotinsky, Shuisky's partner, who I do not quote here) is familiar with what had happened in Uglich. Both passages refer to the Tsarevich's death and that it had been used to achieve a particular political goal. In the first citation Shuisky justifies why he did not reveal the truth about the Uglich happenings. Very similar is the case with the other extract: now it is the Pretender who "explains" to Marina why she will not expose him as an impostor. Both texts quoted are about the possible consequences of the revelation of a truth that is embarrassing for those in power because, if revealed, it may (it w i l l) undermine their legitimacy or upset their calculations in some other way. This is the "moral" that Shuisky and the Pretender offer respectively: the truth itself is not really important and it is not advisable to disclose it if it may be uncomfortable for those who wield power. He who would happen to be incautious enough to disregard this, would soon be s i l e n c e d -- both in the literal and in the figurative sense. Both Shuisky and the Pretender being aware of this, they accordingly play their parts assigned (Shuisky) and taken up (Pretender) respectively. Yet there is a conspicuous difference between these two men's characters. Shuisky is very clever and prudent but he is not a u d a c i o u s enough to make the first and decisive step onto the path that leads to the throne: he did not have the courage to reveal the truth about the happenings in Uglich. The fundamental difference between Shuisky and the Pretender is that while the latter makes advantage of the situation and of the "moral" which that situation "teaches" his partner, the former is not (has not been) in the position to exploit it. It is remarkable that the reason why Shuisky did not then dare is the same as why the Pretender did: both have realized that the coast is clear for only he who sizes up the situation in due time; who comprehends that nobody will upset his plans by revealing the truth because nobody is willing to ruin oneself. This is the clue not only to the Pretender's success but to Godunov's as well. These are the only characters in the play who not only realize this but are able to make use of it. They have both placed themselves in such a position in which they can make the decisive step(s) required for assuming power.

In order to understand Shuisky's figure and the function of this figure it is worthwhile to follow his role in the play. We have already analyzed his discourse with Vorotinsky above. In this scene Shuisky shows himself the absolute master of the situation. Throughout he rules his partner: he so manages the discussion that he can elicit from Vorotinsky everything he wants. Nearly everything what Vorotinsky says is a response to what Shuisky has suggested to him. Thus Shuisky "through simulation" gets hold of his partner's "most secret thoughts".

Shuisky also governs the Shuisky-Pushkin scene despite that it is not he who brings the new information about the pretender but his partner. To some extent the construction of this scene is

parallel with that of the Vorotinsky-Shuisky scene. Shuisky here also manages to make his partner show his cards when he says:

*% , F H \ & " 0 > " b ! 4 , F : 4 * @ > " D @ * "
? > " * @ 6 * , H , H @ \$ Z H \ (D @ 2 , & , : 4 8 @ 6 .*

*This is an important news, and if it reaches the people,
There will be a storm, a terrible one.* (spacings mine,

M.M.)

Pushkin's answer:

*G " 8 @ 6 (D @ 2 , , R H @ & D b * P " D ` # @ D 4 F J
E * , D 0 " H \ & , > , P > " J < > @ 6 (@ : @ & , .*

*Such a storm that tsar Boris
Will hardly hold the crown on his wise head.*

It is obvious that Shuisky says what he says in order to elicit from his partner his "most secret thoughts". And when Pushkin reaches the end of his series of complaints upon Boris, it is clear before Shuisky that Pushkin will probably take sides with the pretender. He has to see this from the fact that the first two lines of Pushkin's complaints contain, in fact, the boyar's wish which comes from the depths of his heart. Finally, Shuisky advises Pushkin to be sensible:

*= @ 2 > " , T \ : 4 ? ? \$ ^ H @ < @ \$ @ & F , <
; Z B @ < @ : R 4 < * @ & D , < , > 4 .*

*You know what? About all this
Let us keep silent for the time being.*

It is clear from this dialogue that of the two of them Shuisky is the stronger character who directs the conversation so that he be able to get hold of his partner's intentions without being forced to reveal his. This is a much more difficult task than it was with the naive and credulous Vorotinsky because Pushkin is an experienced and shrewd politician. This becomes clear on the one hand from the way he tells the news about the emerging of the pretender, on the other hand, from how he persuades Basmanov to take sides with the pretender. Shuisky, however, is not only shrewd and cunning but something more (*I 8 : @ > R 4 & Z 6 , > @ F < , : Z 6 4 : J 8 " & Z 6 - "he is pliable but bold and cunning"*): he is bold but not audacious and therefore will not take sides with the pretender. He precisely knows, from Godunov's example, what end this adventure will bring for the False-Dimitry. In connection with the pretender Shuisky uses the words *J * " , P*

("reckless fellow") and @H&" ("daredevilry"), and with this the poet suggests that the prince is too clever to be as audacious as the pretender; he waits out for the False-Dimitry's interregnum.

The poet builds up the Shuisky-scenes so that in them Shuisky is always a dominant figure. We have seen this in his dialogues with Vorotinsky and Shuisky. One of the motifs in his discourse with Godunov which signify the prince's dominance is his gesture to the tsar to send out the tsarevich before he tells the formidable news. Boris Godunov denies this but when Shuisky reaches the end of his monologue about the danger of the pretender -)4<4HD4b &@F8D,F>J&T., 4<b ("the resuscitated name of Dimitry") -, he immediately sends the tsarevich out of the room. For us the message of this gesture is that Shuisky k n e w i n a d v a n c e that the tsarevich will have to be sent out of the room.

The last scene where Shuisky is on the stage is *The Duma of the Tsar* with the patriarch's miraculous story. What regards the dramaturgy of the scene, it is fully governed by Shuisky (as one of the boyars observes it at the end of the scene). Boris Godunov finds himself in a very awkward situation because the story told by the patriarch has a reference to the dead tsarevich who died in mysterious circumstances. Shuisky refuses the patriarch's absolutely inapt suggestion and brings forward his. All the boyars are embarrassed during the story; it is only Shuisky who gathers strength out of this scene which is the peak of his ability to size up a difficult (political) situation. At this point we can see Shuisky's figure about whom it has become clear that he is the only statesmanlike character in the play; this can neither be said of Godunov or the pretender. Shuisky's figure and actions are composed in such a way that we see in him a man who is always able to size up the situation adequately and is able to be the master of that situation. This happens all four times he enters the stage.

I have pointed out above that the play itself starts with a dialogue about political manipulation. It is remarkable that political machination is not only the s u b j e c t of Scene I but it also serves as its f r a m e. On the one hand, Shuisky and Vorotinsky talk about Godunov's deeds and what is then to be expected. On the other, their discourse is i t s e l f an act of political intrigue. Shuisky, very shrewdly, so directs the conversation that he jockeys his partner into revealing before him his innermost thoughts about Godunov and the supreme power over Russia. Pushkin so builds up this scene that while following the dialogue, we perhaps only suspect that Shuisky is playing a cat-and-mouse game with Vorotinsky. It is only three scenes later that it is explicitly expressed -- by Shuisky himself:

! &BD@R,<, b 2:@F:@&4,< BD4H&@D>Z<
G@(" 0,:" H,\$b :4T\ 4FBZH"H,
%,D>,6 J2>"H\ H&@6 H"6>Z6 @\$D"2 <ZF:;,6.

*Otherwise I then only wished
To try you through simulation*

To get to know your secret thoughts.

This brief conversation, which ends the Coronation Scene, appears to serve as a counterpoise to Boris Godunov's inauguration speech. It is this point that it becomes clear what Shuisky's real intentions were when he was holding that discourse with Vorotinsky in Scene 1. That the poet has placed this brief conversation immediately after Boris' solemn pledge, in which he promises "to govern [his] people in glory and [to be] pious and true", strongly questions the solemnity of the new monarch's oration. Since this speech is Godunov's first appearance in the play, retrospectively not only the speech itself has been deprived of its grand and august character but we will hardly believe that the person uttering that speech is sincere whenever he speaks in public. This reservation of ours is of course not restricted to the title hero; it is applied to more or less everyone in the play who takes part in the political game.

A very similar role is played by the two people-scenes prior to the coronation (Scene 2, *The Red Square* and Scene 3, *On the Dievichye Field. Novodievichy Convent*). The second people-scene is more interesting in this respect: the whole scene is occupied by the people. In the play they have no individual names; they are named *First*, *Second*, *A woman*, etc. They appear to be absolutely indifferent to what is happening; they do not even know why they should have to fall on their knees and cry. There is an amusing moment by the end of the scene when some of the people talk as follows:

?*4>	<i>Everybody is crying,</i>
)DJ(@6	<i>Let's cry too, brother.</i>
A,D&Z6	<i>I am trying hard, brother.</i>
%H@D@6	<i>But I can't.</i>
One of them	<i>Neither can I. Don't you have an onion?</i>
Another	<i>I would rub it in my eyes.</i>
First	<i>No, I'm going to smear them</i>
Second	<i>[with saliva.</i>

Yes, the way it is being expressed that to these people the whole procedure of beseeching their would-be monarch to accept the crown means absolutely nothing is certainly amusing. For

us, the readers, this passage lays more stress on that this is a game which has already been played in advance. Yet the full meaning of the people-scenes becomes clear after we have read the very last lines of Scene 3:

= "D@* %, >, P 2" > 4 <! @> P"D\! @> F@(: "F4:Fb!
@D4F > "T P"D\! * " 2*D"&FH&J,H # @D4F!

First *The crown is his! He's the Tsar! He has agreed!
Boris is our Tsar! Long live Boris!*

So Boris Godunov has finally agreed to accept the throne and is going to be crowned. But we have already seen in what context this had taken place: first we followed Shuisky's cat-and-mouse game with Vorotinsky (and from it learnt about Godunov's murky past), then watched the people's attitude toward its would-be ruler. It was only after that that Boris Godunov appeared as the new legitimate Tsar. As we advance in the course of *Boris Godunov*, it becomes clear that this play is a drama of legitimacy. This means that for the main dramatic characters, who are participants in the struggle for power, legitimacy is the fundamental question -- which can best be obtained from the people. Therefore it has a decisive bearing on the final interpretation of the tragedy that Boris Godunov as Tsar has had to rely on such a legitimacy as he has relied upon since Scene 3 (his people betrays entire indifference to the matter). This shakes his legitimacy to the foundations. But not only his; as it will prove by the end of the play, his opponent's, the Pretender's just as well. As we look back from the end of the drama, the seriousness of the people's beseeching Godunov, as well as of his coronation and his solemn pledge disappears. Such a start seems to determine from the outset the track of the play. After these scenes it is clear that politics is going to play a major role in the drama, and this anticipates the main theme, i.e. that something is rotten in the state.

One of the last scenes in the play is the one that takes place at the general headquarters between Basmanov and the boyar Pushkin. The latter is persuading the former, who is Feodor Godunov's (the new Tsar's) commander-in-chief, to change sides. Pushkin's arguments can be summed up as follows: since the people has acknowledged him as the Tsarevich Dimitry, there is no use to remain loyal to the young Godunov. What the truth is about "Dimitry" does not absolutely matter: e.g. Pushkin, the boyar himself admittedly "would not stand by it". He urges Basmanov to grasp the opportunity and "make [Dimitry] his friend forever" by "proclaiming him Tsar". This dialogue picks up and develops the main theme of the conversation between Marina and the Pretender held by the fountain. There the Pretender said:

... > 4 8 @D@:\, > 4 B"B", > 4 &,\ :< @04
=, *J<"H @ BD"&*, F:@& < @4N.

*...neither the king, nor the pope, nor the nobles
Seek the truth in my words.*

Here Pushkin says:

*C@FF4b 4 94H&"
)4<4HD4,< *"&>@,(@ BD42>":4,
=@, &BD@R,<, b 2" ^H@ >, FH@`.
#ZH\ <@0,H, @>)4<4HD46 >"FH@bV46,
#ZH\ <@0,H, @> 4 F"<@2&">,P. G@:\8@
a &,*", RH@ D">@ 4:4 B@2*>@
+<J ;@F8&J JFHJB4H FZ> %@D4F@&.*

*Russia and Lithuania
Have long since recognized him as Dimitry;
However, I would not stand by this.
It may be that he is the real Dimitry,
It may be that he is only a pretender. But
I know that Boris' son will sooner or later
Yield Moscow to him.*

and a couple of lines later:

*=@ 2>,"T\ :4, R,< F4:\>Z <Z, #"F<">@&?
=, &@6F8@<, >,H, >, B@:\F8@`B@<@/@6,
! <>,>4,<; *"! <>,>4,< >"D@*>Z<.*

*Do you know in what we are strong, Basmanov?
Not in the arms, no, not in the Poles' help
But in the opinion; yes! in the opinion of the people.*

Then he reminds Basmanov:

*)4<4HD4b HZ B@<>4T\ H@D0,FH&@
3 <4D>Z, ,(@ 2"&@,&">\b,
7@(*" &,2*, \$,2 &ZFHD,:",<J
A@F:JT>Z, F**"&":4F\ (@D@*",
! &@,&@* JBDb<ZN R,D>\ &b2":"?*

*Dimitry's triumph
And his peaceful conquests
When everywhere without a shot
The cities surrendered to him
And the mob has tied up unyielding military leaders.*

Basmanov's arguments to remain faithful to the young Feodor show a naïve politician: first he argues that he has sworn for Feodor who "had contemned the hierarchy and the anger of boyars" for him. Then he refers to his military force. Apparently he is not aware of the situation -- as his counterpart in the dialogue is. However naïve may Basmanov be, we would not necessarily regard him as a straightforward man; he is naïve not because he is so ingenuous and innocent but because he shows lack of discernment in judging his situation when he can only rely on himself (before Pushkin enlightens him as to his chances as Feodor Godunov's commander-in-chief). When at the end of the scene he is left alone and is formulating his ponderings on what to do, in his sway he first mentions his "argument" to stand fast by the young Tsar (viz. that he is the monarch's favourite official) which is his only argument on this side. Then he lists three arguments in favour of abandoning Feodor (= "F", "DH", "FH", "D", "Z", "death", "power", "distress of the people") and sounds for the assembly. From this it is, I think, probably clear how he has settled his dilemma.

Each of the two participants in this scene has an uttering which deserves special attention. They have bearing on one another from a poetical viewpoint. Basmanov says to Pushkin in the first half of the scene:

*As long as I stand by the young Tsar,
He will not abandon the throne.*

Basmanov presumably does not suspect how much he is right when he says these words; it is only we, the readers, who at this point conjecture the truth of this sentence. By the end of the play it will have proved true that Feodor has been able to retain the throne only as long as he had Basmanov's support. When that support ceased to exist for him, it automatically meant that his political career, as well as his mortal span, had ended. If we view these two lines retrospectively, after having read the play to the end, we find bitter tragic irony in them.

To Basmanov's statement appears to correspond Pushkin's one and a half lines which at first glance seem to be rather puzzling:

E@ &F, < H&@4< J<@< 4 H&,D @6 &@:;6
=, JFH@4T\;*

*With all your mind and your strong will
You will not stand fast.*

First of all, this sentence gives proof of Pushkin's sagacity and keen insight into human nature. He predicts to Basmanov that he will not stand by Feodor because he will not be able to: he does not have a will strong enough. Secondly, again viewing it retrospectively, the end of the tragedy will perhaps recall what Pushkin says here: the young Tsar is overthrown and murdered because his commander-in-chief failed to stand fast.⁶ This is again a striking example of our poet's dramatic irony.

This discourse between Basmanov and Pushkin evokes in the attentive reader the dialogue between Vorotinsky and Shuisky in the first scene of the play. It is not only the subject of the conversation (the truth about the Tsarevich and the consequences to be expected) that provides a link between the two scenes but also the relation of the two speakers in each dialogue. Pushkin and Shuisky are the shrewd "adherents of political realism" who can gauge the situation properly while their counterparts cannot. The poetic technique followed in the two scenes is also the same: Basmanov, as Vorotinsky in Scene 1, serves as a foil to stress his partner's sagacity and cynicism. Yet there are significant differences in the dramatic role of the two scenes. Scene 1 serves to introduce the political motif into the play and the part of one of the two characters (Vorotinsky) is limited to lay emphasis on the other. On the other hand, in the Basmanov--Pushkin scene Basmanov's figure is not restricted to the role of the foil which brings into relief the counterpart's character. This scene is the peak of the political machination represented in the drama. As I have said, from the view of the composition Basmanov's figure here plays a very similar role to Vorotinsky's in the scene with Shuisky: it is the contrast which serves to lay special emphasis on the figure of the inaugurated and calculating politician. The seemingly "innocent" discourse between Shuisky and Vorotinsky in the beginning of the play, due to Pushkin's fine poetic construction, has by the end of the play proved the main organizing force not only of the plot but also of the composition. On the level of the plot this dialogue between Basmanov and the boyar Pushkin is the point that decides the fate of Boris Godunov's family and thus determines the end of the drama. It can therefore be said that this impersonal political manipulation plays a major role in the drama; so major a role that it evidently questions the seriousness and grandeur in everybody who to any extent takes part in this political game. The way the individual scenes are arranged in the play show Pushkin's ironic attitude toward all the characters that take part in the struggle for power which is the basic action of *Boris Godunov*. The pathos of these characters' diction proves false in the mirror of the composition of the drama. Just as in the light of the dialogue between Shuisky and Vorotinsky and the subsequent people--scenes we refuse to believe in the pathos of Godunov's

speech, which he delivers upon his coronation, similarly we will have doubts about everybody's sincerity and straightforwardness who is affected personally in the political game. Pushkin has composed the beginning of his drama in this manner in order that the reader (or the public in the theatre) take with serious reservations what those characters say and act who are involved in this tug-of-war. There is only one scene the grandeur of which is not questioned: it is Pimen and Grigory's scene in the Chudov monastery. Pimen's exquisite diction lends to his character dignity and majesty void of pathos. He keeps this trait of his throughout the scene. The role of this scene is, I think, to show that despite the perfidity and insincerity this turbulence and discord evokes from all the participants without exception, there is somebody who can rise above the momentary interests of the political forces. Pimen is the chronicler who we can always believe, and can retain our belief in him throughout the play: everything what happens in the drama only justifies him and what he has said. It seems very fit to say here that there are firm grounds for asserting that in Pimen's figure Pushkin intended to pay homage to the historian. Whether to Karamzin or Tacitus,⁷ it does not really matter; I am disposed to believe that homage is paid to chronicle-writing (historiography). (The other figure in the drama who is not involved in the political machination is Nikolka, the simpleton. Regarding his function, he is parallel with Pimen in that he too is justified at the end.)⁸

Godunov's (temporary) advantage, sc. that in the decisive moment he dared to make that step, will ruin him in the long run: his formidable opponent will conquer him with that very weapon with which he had then managed to assure power for himself. It is now the Pretender who is in possession of that weapon, since it is he who "could marvellously delude two nations" and thus take advantage of his opponent. The similarities of their way to power are striking indeed: was it not Boris Godunov who had also *d e l u d e d h i s n a t i o n* before he came to the throne? Although the Pretender defeats his adversary by seizing that decisive weapon, he too cannot avoid his fate which proves to be exactly the same as his predecessor's: he is rejected by his own people. True, he does not die in the play⁹ as Godunov, yet the way he leaves the scene is totally disillusioning. His people straightaway loses its infatuation for him when he commits exactly the same crime as his predecessor: he has the legitimate monarch (a young boy)¹⁰ murdered. He is repudiated by the people right at the beginning of his reign for he has committed a decisive fault: he failed to calculate on his people's ethical standpoint when he ordered the assassination of Godunov's son.¹¹ It can therefore be said that the Pretender's legitimacy stands on far less firm grounds than his opponent's did: while the people's hatred toward Godunov gradually develops in the period of his rule and reaches its climax in the scene "The Square Before the Cathedral in Moscow" (this takes place not long before the Tsar's death), the people turns away from the False-Dimitry *b e f o r e* the latter would formally ascend the throne.

Boris Godunov is a tragic figure but the same cannot be applied to the Pretender. There is greatness in the former as he fails to comprehend the new political situation around him and succumbs but there is no greatness in how his antagonist makes advantage of this situation.

Godunov fails to understand (or understands only too late) that his state and the conditions around him have changed while, on the other hand, his adversary fully appreciates the new state of things. Therefore he always has the advantage of Godunov; and, of course, as a genuine politician, he pushes this advantage relentlessly.

We see that the situation at the end of the drama is very similar to the beginning, viz. the legitimate Tsar (or Tsarevich) has been assassinated and a usurper is mounting the throne. Pushkin does not show what is going to happen to the Pretender in the time of his reign. This is certainly not because the poet could count on his audience's being familiar with the possible "sequel" of the drama (since Karamzin's *History* -- Pushkin's source for *Boris Godunov* -- was a popular work in its time, people who either saw or read the play must have been aware of how False Dimitry I had ended his career).¹² When the course of the drama reaches the point where the Pretender has v i r t u a l l y seized power,¹³ Pushkin's image of history has already taken its clear shape and there is no need for him to repeat the course of the drama. It is clear that in many respects we have returned to the starting-point of the play. For right after the young Tsar, Godunov's son has been murdered, something happens in the tragedy that has a great significance not only in the course of the plot but also on the level of the poetic composition: the last sentence of the play () " 2*D"&FH&J,H P"D\)4<4HD46 3&">@&4R! - "Long live Tsar Dimitry Ivanovich") automatically evokes the beseeching scene, especially the very last sentence in it:)" 2*D"&FH&J,H #@D4F! ("Long live Tsar Boris"). As if everything was to repeat itself. It is the question of legitimacy that is at stake at this point a n e w. History in Pushkin's view, as it can be grasped from *Boris Godunov* (which is his only historical drama), may be compared with an orbit in which the planet named HUMAN SOCIETY returns at the end to its starting-point or anyway very close to it. Yet one remarkable change in the position of our "planet" can certainly be perceived. It lies in the people's state of mind. For it is the state of mind of the people that both Godunov based his legitimacy on and the Pretender, together with his allies and supporters, very skilfully calculated upon. On the other hand, this constituent has been "responsible" for both Godunov's fall and the Pretender's losing his legitimacy.

At this point we have got back to the question of the tragic in the figures of the two main contestants. Though there are many things that are common in both of them (both have the legitimate Tsar[evich] murdered, both are usurpers and both are denied their people's assent to be legitimate rulers), it is only Godunov of the two of them who is a tragic character: in the course of the drama it is he who falls and not his opponent-successor. After what had happened in the last scene to Feodor, the Pretender's subsequent fate is no more interesting for the poet (and for us). Of course not so much for moral as artistic reasons: after Godunov had succumbed, his family been exterminated and the usurper had seized power, it has come full circle and, if the poet were to continue the plot, everything could begin all over again. This would follow from the artistic logic of this drama. All that can be said in *one* play has been authentically said and it would be totally needless to repeat it. One might, of course, play with the idea of continuing the story -- in a n o t h e r tragedy. T h i s c o u l d m a k e u p t h e t

heme of a new play, -- but our present play is over at this point.¹⁴

Notes

¹ ARISTOTELIS *De arte poetica*, IX.

² The translation from Greek is mine.

³ Ibid.

⁴ This is true even if we consider that in the entire corpus of Greek tragedies (upon which Aristotle alone relied when he was elaborating his theory of drama) that has survived to us there is only one single work which takes its subject from history. This is Aeschylus' *Persians* and even this one could hardly be defined satisfactorily in the modern sense as a historical drama for it is rather a kind of mythicized history.

⁵ This line is a good proof that it is not grammatical rules that principally govern live human speech since, as we have seen in this example, semantical and grammatical subordination does not necessarily meet.

⁶ On the verbal level the link between Pushkin's and Basmanov's statements is provided by the phrases *stand by* and *stand fast* respectively (in the Russian text *FH@`2"* and *JFH@4T*).

⁷ Karamzin not once refers to Tacitus by offering parallels in Boris Godunov's reign with the time of Tiberius and Nero. It is, therefore, very much probable that Karamzin had read Tacitus. What is more important for us is that Pushkin himself as a *p o e t a d o c t u s* had also been familiar with Tacitus' works.

⁸ Mussorgsky exploits this very finely by placing the Simpleton's brief monologue at the very end of his opera.

⁹ According to Karamzin's records in his *History of the Russian State*, False-Dimitry I died an abominable death after having reigned for a period of about ten months (from 21 July, 1605 to 17 May, 1606): he was said to have been severely beaten and then executed after his mock-trial. I call it a "mock-trial" because when he was tried there was no question of what the sentence would be for him. The aim of the "legal(?)" procedure was not at all to *j u d g e* whether he was guilty or not; his judges definitely knew *i n a d v a n c e* what sentence to pass on him, and they carried out that sentence themselves. Oh, whence springst thou, noble tradition of East-European mock-trials of the 20th-century!

¹⁰ Boris Godunov's son, Feodor was then about sixteen years old.

¹¹ If during his reign the False Dimitry were to come across the imbecile Nikolka, the latter would certainly have flung this act of his in his face.

¹² See fn. 9. For the detailed account of these events see Karamzin vol. XI, chapter IV.

¹³ V i r t u a l l y, because at this point he is d e f a c t o not the ruler yet: he is just to be crowned.

¹⁴ Dostoevsky did not continue *Crime and Punishment* in a "new story". Neither did Pushkin *Boris Godunov*. Nevertheless, the False Dimitry's fate would surely "deserve a mass", if in the form of a dramatic play. It would be a very interesting artistic experiment to write the sequel of Pushkin's *Boris Godunov* as both the story and the phenomenon are very topical in today's Eastern Europe.

Résumé

?B4D"bF\ >" @HDZ&84 42 A@^H484 !D4FH@H,:b, b @BD,*,;b` B@>bH4,
4FH@D4R,F8@6 *D"<Z 4 & @\$V,< 4 & F&b24 F HD"(*4,6 AJT84>" #@D4F '@*J>@&.
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